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ABSTRACT

For centuries, electrical energy has become essential in all sectors of life, both in highly industrialized countries and in developing ones. Its production requires a lot of human, financial and material resources, sometimes having negative consequences on the environment. Optimizing its consumption would be essential given the increasingly growing need, especially in a university environment. The general objective of this study is to effectively size the air conditioning system of the computer rooms of the Higher Institute of Technology of Mamou, Guinea, taking into account the specific thermal loads generated by the computer equipment and the local environmental conditions. The study methodology involved measuring the dimensions of the room, evaluating the thermal loads of the different walls, determining the interior volume, and analyzing the different loads due to heat transmission, such as glazing, air renewal, people, lighting, computers, and video projectors. The results indicate a heat transmission surface of 214 m², with varying thermal loads for each wall. The power of the air conditioner was chosen at 27 kW, with a total number of 12 units. The total thermal loads, including transmissions through walls, glazing, air exchange, people, lighting, computers, and video projectors, were estimated at 118028.8437 KJ/J.

Keywords: Sizing, thermal comfort, air conditioning, Mamou, Guinea.

1. INTRODUCTION

The building sector now ranks among the three major energy consumers in the world with the transport and industrial sectors [1-3]. The share of energy consumption in the building sector amounts to 40% of global energy [2, 4] and 50% of this annual consumption is generally caused by heating, ventilation and air conditioning systems. air conditioning [5]. Furthermore, almost half of building energy consumption is spent on air conditioners in developed countries [6, 2].

In Guinea, habitats have been built until today without respecting standards energy and environmental. Indeed, it appears that the charges are high for the consumers not aware of the convenient use of electrical energy. For this purpose, the energy consumption in the housing sector and others costs the State a financial cost of 1,200 billion Guinean francs per year, or 107,426,770 euros (one hundred and seven million and four twenty-six thousand seven hundred and seventy thousand euros), according to the Ministry of Energy and Hydraulics [7]. Air conditioning is the technique of modifying, controlling and regulating the climatic conditions (temperature, humidity, dust level, etc.) of a room for reasons of comfort (offices, individual homes) or for technical reasons (medical laboratories, premises for manufacturing electronic components, operating theaters, computer rooms) [8].

Nowadays, air conditioning in buildings is an essential system for the comfort of occupants. Indeed, the Republic of Guinea is a hot and humid tropical country. This climatic situation requires a more specific approach for the well-being of occupants, in particular thermal comfort [9].

Heating, ventilation and air conditioning (HVAC) systems provide people working or living inside buildings with “conditioned air” so that they have a comfortable and safe environment. The term "air conditioning" means that the air must be clean and the temperature, humidity and air movement must be within certain acceptable comfort ranges. The American Society of Heating, Refrigerating and Air Conditioning Engineers [10, 11] has established standards that describe thermally acceptable indoor comfort conditions for 80% or more of building occupants. Generally, these comfort conditions, sometimes called “comfort zone”, are between 20 and 24 °C in winter and between 23 and 26 °C in summer [11-13].

Building air conditioning has received a lot of attention in recent years, both in academia and industry. Indeed, in the building sector, HVAC systems represent between 40 and 60% of energy consumption in Europe and more than 50% in the United States [14-15]. Savings linked to HVAC systems are therefore a natural objective of many research groups working to achieve economically competitive solutions, capable of reducing the external energy demand necessary to guarantee comfort conditions. The percentages mentioned above largely depend on many variables, such as climate zone (solar irradiation and temperature), building type, building design and envelope quality, electricity consumption profiles and the efficiency of the installation.

Energy consumption for air conditioning purposes is expected to face an increase in demand over the next 30 years [16-17]. This is for example clearly demonstrated by the fact that in recent years considerable growth in the air conditioning and heat pump market has been observed worldwide, especially in developing countries [17,18].

This increase can be explained by changes in public perception regarding climate and comfort requirements; space cooling, for example, is quickly moving from luxury to necessity, leading to a rapidly growing market. Concerning energy consumption for space heating, even if it has not seen such a significant increase in recent years, according to the Buildings Performance Institute Europe, it still represents the most energy-intensive consumption.

Thermal comfort is considered as an aspect of a sustainable building in almost all sustainable building assessment methods and tools [11,20].

The assessment of the thermal environment and thermal comfort in an air-conditioned room is essential to estimate the performance of air conditioning systems. At present, the thermal environment testing of a room equipped with an air conditioner follows the GB/T 33658 standard [21, 22] in China. However, multiple parameters related to structure and control affect the performance of air conditioning systems as well as the thermal environments of air-conditioned rooms. To improve the efficiency and speed of testing, it is important to identify an effective method to predict and evaluate the indoor thermal environments of air-conditioned rooms [23-27].

In 2017 according to the International Energy Agency, 1.6 billion air conditioners were operating worldwide, approximately 50% of which were in the United States and China. In that same year, the world consumed nearly 3,900 TWh of energy for cooling homes and offices, refrigerating food and medicine, etc. This is approximately 3% to 4% of final energy consumption. according to Toby Peters. Demand is expected to “explode in the coming decades” according to the IEA, which could increase energy consumption used for refrigeration and air conditioning by around 90% by 2050 according to the University of Birmingham during the first congress dedicated to “clean cold” (April 2018) [28].

It is to respond to these worrying requests that we have proposed to make our contribution to the resolution of problems in the energy and environmental fields in general and in particular the case of Guinea by treating this theme entitled: sizing of an active air conditioning system for thermal comfort in the computer rooms of the Higher Institute of Technology of Mamou, Guinea.

2. MATERIALS AND METHOD

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2.1. Materials

2.1.1. Presentation of the study area

Located 4km from the town of Mamou, the IST is limited to the east by the Abattoir district, to the west by the Téliço district, to the north by the National School of Forestry Environment (ENATEF) on the national road Mamou-Conakry, to the South by the Tchèhol district. It has an altitude of 1000 to 2000 m and extends between latitude 10°21' North and longitude 12°06' South. The temperature varies between 21°C and 27°C with an average rainfall of around 1651mm (see figure 1).

Figure 1: location of the study area

2.1.2. Work tools

Tools being all the objects which serve as working materials in a project or any other work for the realization of a work. As part of our work we used the following tools or materials: the tape: which was used to determine the dimensions of the rooms; scale: used to determine heights; the thermometer: which was used to determine the exterior and interior temperatures of air-conditioned premises; thermo flash: which was used to control the temperatures of air-conditioned premises; notepad: used to mention information taken in the field.

2.2. Method

For the execution of this work, we used the manual method and the empirical relationships which come into play in the determination of the different air conditioning parameters.

2.2.1. Input data

The temperatures of the interior and exterior walls of the computer rooms and the ambient air were taken during the months of (December, January, February, March) which are considered to be unfavorable periods in terms of comfort for our area. study. These different temperatures are recorded in table 1.

Table 1 Different Temperatures

Times	Outside					Interior				
	Tex	East	West	North	South	Tin	East	West	North	South
10h 00mn	26	29	28	28	28	22	28	23	25	28
10h 30mn	27	30	29	29	31	22	29	25	25	29
11h 00mn	28	31	30	29	32	25	29	26	26	30
11h 30mn	30	32	30	30	33	26	30	27	26	30
12h 00mn	32	33	31	31	34	28	30	28	29	30

12h 30mn	34	34	31	32	35	29	30	29	29	33
Total	30	32	30	30	32	25	29	26	27	30

The graphs of the different temperature ranges taken are shown in Figures 2 and 3. In these figures, we see that the temperatures of the exterior walls increase considerably compared to the temperatures of the interior walls from 10 a.m. to 12 p.m. and beyond 12 p.m. the temperatures the exterior walls begin to drop to the detriment of the internal walls.

Figure 2: Indoor temperature of computer rooms

Figure 3: Outdoor temperature of computer rooms

2.2.2. Sizing and determination of the different loads of the air conditioning system

A) External thermal loads

They constitute the loads due to heat input by transmission through the envelope of the cold room, loads due to the opening of the doors, loads due to glazing and loads due to air renewal.

These charges are determined as follows:

Thermal loads by transmission through external walls

The thermal loads by transmission through the walls (North; South; West and East) are determined by the expression:

$$Q_{par} = 24 \times k \times S \times \Delta T \times \alpha \tag{1}$$

Where :

Q_{par} : thermal load by transmission through the external walls ;

24 : Length of a day in hours (h) ;

K : Overall heat exchange coefficient in [W/m²°C] ;

S : Surface of the wall through which the energy is supplied in [m²] ;

ΔT : Temperature difference between external and internal walls [(°C)] ;

α : Correction coefficient for opaque walls.

a) Determination of heat transmission surface

This surface is determined by the following relation :

$$S = \sqrt{S_{ex} \times S_{in}} \quad (2)$$

With :

S_{ex} : total surface area of exterior walls [m²];

S_{in} : total surface area of interior walls [m²].

✓ Thermal load by transmission through the east wall

This thermal load due to the east wall is determined by the relationship :

$$Q_{murest} = 24 \times K \times S_{netmurest} \times \Delta T_{est} \times \alpha \quad (3)$$

Where :

Q_{murest} : thermal load east wall ;

24 : length of a day in hours (h) ;

K : Overall transmission coefficient due to bricks and thickness [W/m²°C] ;

$S_{netmurest}$ = Net surface of the east wall (m²) ;

ΔT_{est} : temperature difference ($T_{ex_{est}} - T_{in_{est}}$) [(°C)] ;

$T_{ex_{est}}$: exterior temperature of the wall to be air-conditioned taken equal to 32°C;

$T_{in_{est}}$: interior temperature of the wall to be air-conditioned taken equal to 29°C ;

α : Opaque wall correction coefficient.

By analogy, the thermal loads of the West, North and South walls are determined by the following relationships:

✓ Thermal load by transmission through the west wall

Let us determine the thermal load due to the west wall by the relation:

$$Q_{muroest} = 24 \times K \times S_{netmuroest} \times \Delta T_{ouest} \times \alpha \quad (4)$$

✓ Thermal load by transmission through the North wall

Let us determine the thermal load due to the North wall by the relation:

$$Q_{mumord} = 24 \times K \times S_{netmurnord} \times \Delta T_{nord} \times \alpha \quad (5)$$

✓ Thermal load by transmission through the South wall

Let us determine the thermal load due to the North wall by the relation:

$$Q_{mursud} = 24 \times K \times S_{netmursud} \times \Delta T_{sud} \times \alpha \quad (6)$$

✓ Thermal loads by opening doors

The thermal loads by opening the doors [Q_{op} (kJ)] are given by the following relationship:

$$Q_{op} = 24 \left[8 + (0,067 \times \Delta T_p) \right] t_p \times l_p \times H_p \left[H_p \times \left(1 - \frac{\rho_{ex}}{\rho_{in}} \right) \right]^{1/2} (\text{hex} - \text{hin}) C_{ra} \quad (7)$$

With:

$$t_p = \frac{d_p \times \rho_j}{24} \quad (8)$$

24 : Length of a day in hours (h);

t_p : Door opening time [min/h];

l_p : door width [m];

H_p : Door height [m];

d_p : Door opening time (back and forth) [mn/h];

ρ_j : Daily flow [ton/day];

hex : Specific enthalpy of the air outside the cold room [kJ/kg];

h_{in} : Specific enthalpy of the air inside the cold room [kJ/kg];
 ρ_{ex} : Degree of humidity of the air outside the cold room [%];
 ρ_{in} : Degree of humidity of the air inside the cold room [%];
 C_{ra} : Reduction due to the possible presence of an air curtain (door without curtain, $C_{ra} = 1$ door with curtain, $C_{ra} = 0,25$).

In the case of a cold room with a door, the thermal loads are not reduced by opening the doors.. So: $Q_{op} = 0$

✓ **Thermal loads due to glazing (doors and windows)**

The thermal loads due to glazing [$Q_{vit}(kJ)$] are estimated by the relationship :

$$Q_{vit} = 24 \times K \times S_{vit} \times \Delta T \times \alpha \quad (9)$$

Where :

24 : Length of a day in hours (h) ;

K : Overall glass transmission coefficient ;

S : Door surface and windows [m^2] ;

ΔT : Temperature difference in the room to be air-conditioned ($T_{ex} - T_{in}$) ;

T_{ex} : Outside temperature of the room to be air-conditioned taken equal to 30 °C ;

T_{in} : Interior temperature of the room to be air-conditioned taken equal to 25°C ;

α : Correction coefficient which is given according to the characteristics of the elements of the room to be air-conditioned.

For the case of our research, we will use double glazing and metal joinery including ($\alpha = 0,87$ and $K = 3,95$ W/ m^2K).

• **Thermal loads due to the glazing of all computer rooms**

The total thermal load received by the glazing of computer rooms is given by the relation (10).

$$Q_{vittot} = Q_{vit} \times n \quad (10)$$

Where : $n = 4$, which represents the number of computer rooms.

✓ **Thermal loads due to air renewals**

For the physiological needs of the human body, it is necessary to provide a certain quantity of fresh air to the occupants of the room to be air-conditioned. This supply of fresh air generates additional loads in sensible and latent heat. These heats are estimated as follows:

- Sensible heat

$$Q_{rsen} = t \times \tau_{sen} \times q_{vi} \times (T_{ex} - T_{in}) \quad (11)$$

- Latent heat

$$Q_{rlat} = t \times \tau_{lat} \times q_{vi} \times (T_{ex} - T_{in}) \quad (12)$$

With :

$t = 6$ h/j : Operating time of the room to be air-conditioned ;

τ : Air volume heat;

$\tau_{sen} = 0,34$ Wh/ $m^3.k$;

$\tau_{lat} = 0,825$ Wh/ $m^3.k$;

T_{ex} Outside temperature of the room to be air-conditioned taken equal to 30 °C ;

T_{in} : Interior temperature of the room to be air-conditioned taken equal to 25°C ;

q_{vi} : Volume flow in m^3/h .

V_{in} : Interior volume of the room to be air-conditioned ;

$L_{in} = 9,770$ m : Interior length of the room to be air-conditioned ;

$L_{in} = 9,000$ m : Interior width of the room to be air-conditioned ;

$H_{in} = 2,970$ m : Interior height of the room to be air-conditioned.

Where :

$$q_{vi} = R \times V_{in} \quad (13)$$

$$V_{in} = L_{in} \times l_{in} \times H_{in} \quad (14)$$

R : air renewal rate depending on the volume of the room to be air-conditioned. These different values are recorded in the table below.

Table 2: Value of the air renewal rate (R) depending on the volume of the rooms

Chamber	R	Chamber	R	Chamber	R	Chamber	R
---------	---	---------	---	---------	---	---------	---

volume	-	+	volume	-	+	volume	-	+	volume	-	+
02,5	52	70	20	16,5	22,0	100	6,8	9,0	600	2,50	3,20
03,0	47	63	25	14,5	19,5	150	5,4	7,0	800	2,10	2,80
04,0	40	53	30	13,0	17,5	200	4,6	6,0	1000	1,90	2,40
05,0	35	47	40	11,5	15,0	250	4,1	5,3	1500	1,50	1,95
07,5	29	38	50	10,0	13,0	300	3,7	4,8	2000	1,30	1,65
10,0	24	32	60	09,0	12,0	400	3,1	4,1	2500	1,10	1,45
13,0	19	20	80	07,7	10,0	500	2,8	3,0	≥3000	1,05	1,30

For the volume of our positive cold room which is equal to 261 m³, the air renewal rate is 5.3.

- **Thermal loads due to air changes in all computer rooms**

The total thermal loads are given by the relation:

$$Q_{\text{retot}} = Q_{\text{re}} \times n \quad (15)$$

$n = 4$: number of rooms to be air-conditioned.

- **B) number of rooms to be air-conditioned**

These charges are classified into two categories: dependent and independent charges of people. They constitute the loads due to people, loads due to lighting, loads due to machines (computers and video projectors).

- ✓ **Thermal loads due to people**

The thermal loads due to people [Q_{per} (kJ)] are given by the following relationship :

$$Q_{\text{per}} = P_{\text{th}} \times t \times n \quad (16)$$

$P_{\text{th}} = 142 \text{ kcal/h} = 0.165 \text{ kW}$: Power emitted by a person seated while typing quickly ;

$n = 50$: number of students occupying a computer room in the computer engineering department ;

$t = 6 \text{ h/j}$: Operating time of the room to be air-conditioned per day.

- **Thermal load due to people in all computer rooms**

The total thermal load is given by the relationship (17).

$$Q_{\text{pertot}} = Q_{\text{per}} \times n \quad (17)$$

$n = 4$ number of computer rooms in the computer engineering department to be air-conditioned.

- ✓ **Thermal loads due to lighting**

The thermal loads due to lighting [Q_{ec} (kJ)] are given by relation (18).

- For incandescent lamps (40W/m²), the following relationship gives these loads.

$$Q_{\text{ec}} = P_n \times t \times n \quad (18)$$

- For fluorescent lamps with (10W/m²), the following relationship gives these charges.

$$Q_{\text{ec}} = \tau \times P_n \times t \times n \quad (19)$$

P_n : Rated power of a lamp ;

t : Room lighting time in hours per day ;

n : Number of lamps in a room;

τ : Power factor addressed by the lamp ballast.

For our positive cold room, we will use waterproof fluorescent lamps which are more resistant to the cold. They are determined by the relationship (19).

Where :

[Ekott *et al.*, 12(12): December, 2023]
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$P_n = 36 \text{ W} = 0.036 \text{ kW}$: Rated power of a lamp ;
 $t = 6 \text{ h/j}$: Room lighting time in hours per day;
 $n = 12$: Number of lamps in a room ;
 $\tau = 1.15$: Power factor addressed by the lamp ballast.

- **Thermal load due to lighting in all computer rooms**

The total thermal load is given by relation (17).

- ✓ **Thermal loads due to various machines :**
- **Computer**

The thermal loads due to the various machines (computers) [$Q_{or}(kJ)$] are given by the relation (20):

$$Q_{or} = P_d \times t \times n \quad (20)$$

Where :

$P_d = 75 \text{ W} = 0.075 \text{ kW}$: is the power released by an active computer;

$t = 6 \text{ h/j}$: Operating time of the air-conditioned room per day;

$n = 50$ number of computers per room.

- **Thermal load due to various machines (computer) in all computer rooms**

The total thermal load is given by the following relation :

$$Q_{ortat} = Q_{or} \times n \quad (21)$$

$n = 4$: number of computer rooms to be air-conditioned.

2- Thermal loads due to various machines Vidéoprojecteur

The thermal loads due to the various machines (video projector) [$Q_{vidpro}(kJ)$] are given by the following relationship:

$$Q_{vidpro} = P_{vidpro} \times t \quad (22)$$

Where :

$P_{vidpro} = 2000 \text{ lumens} = 0.2 \text{ kW}$: is the power of the video projector;

$T = 6 \text{ h/j}$: operating time of the room to be air-conditioned;

$n = 1$: number of video projectors in an air-conditioned room.

- **Thermal load due to various machines (video projector) in all computer rooms.**

The total heat load is given by formula (23)

$$Q_{vidprotot} = Q_{vidpro} \times n \quad (23)$$

$$Q_{vidprotot} = Q_{vidpro} \times n \quad (23)$$

$n = 4$: number of computer rooms to be air-conditioned.

a) Determination of power

The amount of cooling an air conditioner must provide to maintain comfortable conditions is the cooling load. It also varies depending on the dimensions of the room, the orientation of the windows, the amount of insulation in the attic and walls, the amount of heat produced in the room, etc.

This power is the ratio between the sum of all total daily loads (Q_{cqt}) and the operating time of the room to be air conditioned ($t = 6\text{h/j}$).

$$P_c = \frac{Q_{cqt}}{t} \text{ [kW]} \quad (24)$$

b) Choice of air conditioner

There are a multitude of air conditioning systems including the cooling capacity, the operating principle and the field of application as well as the advantages and disadvantages that one system presents compared to another.

For our case, the choice is made for a split-system air conditioner with a power range of 6 to 200 kW.

The power of the split system on the market is 30.000 BTU.

✓ **Number of air conditioner**

$$N = \frac{P_{\text{total}}}{P_{\text{climatiseur}}} \quad (25)$$

Where :

Ptotal : the total power of the air conditioning system;

Pclim : the power of an air conditioner.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The various results obtained as part of this study are described as follows:

The results concerning the dimensions of the room, the wall loads, the power of the air conditioner and the number of air conditioners.

Table 3.1: Summary of room parameters to be air-conditioned

N°	Parameters	Values	Units
1	Transmission area	214	m ²
2	East wall thermal load	25404,8296	KJ
3	West wall thermal load	36032,0314	KJ
4	North wall thermal load	33955,1896	KJ
5	South wall thermal load	22636,7931	KJ
6	Interior volume of the room to be air-conditioned	261	m ³
7	Air conditioner power	27	kW
8	Total number air conditioner	12	-

In this table, we have listed the results concerning the heat transmission surface, the different thermal loads received by the walls, the interior volume of the room to be air conditioned, the power of the air conditioner and the total number of air conditioners. We see through these results that the thermal load received by the west wall is higher than the loads received by the other walls. This would be due to the fact that in Guinea, the sun rises in the east and sets in the west, reaching its maximum in terms of solar flux from 12 p.m., which influences the propagation of heat towards the wall. west. This proves that the west and north walls are the most exposed to solar radiation than the east and south walls in the case of our study. The unit power of the air conditioner is 27,000W, with three (3) air conditioners per computer room, giving a total of twelve (12) air conditioners for all the computer rooms to be air conditioned.

The results concerning the different loads due to heat transmission

Table 3.2: Thermal loads of chamber components

N°	Thermal loads	Symbols	Values (kJ/j)
1	Transmission through walls	Q _{par}	118028,8437
2	Glazing	Q _{vit}	15040,1584
3	Air renewal	Q _{re}	174046,806
4	People	Q _{per}	178200
5	Lighting	Q _{ec}	10730,88
6	Computers	Q _{or}	81000
7	Video projectors	Q _{vidpro}	4320

8	Total charges	Q_T	581366,6881
9	Increase in charges (safety factor 1%Qt)	$Q_{majorée}$	5813,666881
Total daily charges (total charges + $Q_{majorée}$)		Q_{cqt}	587180,35498

This graph below illustrates the different thermal loads depending on our results recorded in the table above.

Figure 4: thermal load graph

In this figure, we see that the heat transmitted by people is higher than the heat transmitted by other loads. This explains why the heat released by people consumes much more energy than other loads. After the transmission of heat by people, we have the loads by air renewal which ranks second in terms of energy consumption with an amount of 174046.806 KJ/J. while the heat transmitted by video projectors consumes less energy than others, which is around 4320 KJ/J.

4. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, this precise sizing of the air conditioning system aims to ensure optimal environmental conditions for the preservation of sensitive IT equipment. Future research perspectives could explore energy efficiency, intelligent management of the air conditioning system, and the impact of technological developments on the thermal loads of computer rooms, thus contributing to the continuous improvement of IT installations. These results are crucial to guarantee the sustainability and performance of IT infrastructures in a specific local context.

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